

A Master of Science project submitted to the
Graduate Program at the Institute of Physics, University of São Paulo

Title: Estimating the aerosol direct radiative effect from remote sensing at two locations in Brazil

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Abstract

Aerosols influence Earth's climate by directly altering solar and terrestrial radiation and indirectly modifying cloud properties. Yet, their total impact remains one of the least understood components of the climate system. This project aims to quantify the aerosol direct radiative effect, which measures the perturbation in the top-of-atmosphere radiative flux caused solely by aerosols in a cloud-free atmosphere, in two regions of Brazil, the southern Amazon Basin and the Metropolitan Area of São Paulo. To achieve this, we will integrate remotely sensed aerosol data from ground-based sunphotometer measurements with data from recently launched spaceborne sensors. These datasets will yield a characterization of aerosol optical and physical properties, including their size distribution, refractive index, scattering phase function, and vertical extinction profile, as well as surface reflectance properties. We will then use a radiative transfer code package to simulate top-of-atmosphere fluxes under both aerosol-free and aerosol-laden conditions, allowing us to derive the aerosol direct radiative effect at the two target locations. The results to be obtained in this project will help build a better understanding of the impact of aerosols on the climate system by characterizing their radiative effect in two locations in Brazil.

1. Introduction

Atmospheric aerosols are composed of microscopic particles that can affect the climate by interacting directly with solar and terrestrial radiation, as well as indirectly through changes in the optical properties of clouds (Haywood, 2021). Aerosols and their interaction with clouds are among the least understood contributors to climate change, and understanding their role is crucial for gaining a better understanding of the climate (IPCC, 2023). The quantity, particle size, shape, and chemical composition of aerosols are essential factors in determining their radiative impact on existing ecosystems and urban settings, which depends on the properties of aerosol sources present at each location (Yu and Zhang, 2011).

In the Amazon Basin, the natural biome contributes to both primary aerosol sources, i.e., particles directly emitted by vegetation, and secondary sources, in which volatile organic compounds emitted by vegetation are subsequently oxidized in the atmosphere to form aerosol particles (Martin et al., 2010). Other natural sources in the Amazon include sea salt near coastal areas, local and long-range transported dust (Martin et al., 2010). Between August and October each year, however, anthropogenic biomass burning smoke is the most prevalent source of aerosols in the region, especially in the southern Amazon Basin (Ten Hoeve et al., 2012). Amazonian smoke aerosol particles are also transported downwind and spread across large fractions of the South American continent (Martins et al., 2018). These particles induce micro- and macrophysical changes in cloud properties (Correia et al., 2021) and may change precipitation patterns.

Another significant anthropogenic aerosol source in South America is the pollution originating from vehicular combustion, particularly in large urban areas such as the Metropolitan

Area of São Paulo (MASP). Vehicle displacement contributes to both primary and secondary aerosols and is also associated with the resuspension of soil dust (Pereira et al., 2024). In particular, the gas and particulate phases of pollution in the megacity of São Paulo are influenced by both the vehicular combustion of fossil fuels, primarily diesel and gasoline, as well as the use of renewable fuels in the form of ethanol (Brito et al., 2015). Adding to this complex scenario, the MASP can also be impacted by long-range transported biomass burning aerosols (Pereira et al., 2021; Yamasoe et al., 2017).

The aerosol direct radiative effect (ADRE, or ϵ_a), a parameter that quantifies the overall impact of a location's aerosol sources over the Earth's energy balance, has been used worldwide by the scientific community to measure aerosols' influence at remote locations such as the Amazon Basin, in urban settings, over the ocean, and other places. Given surface reflectance properties for a specific area and representative aerosol parameters (discussed in Section 2) at that location, ϵ_a can be modelled using a radiative transfer code, such as libRadtran (Emde et al., 2016; Mayer and Kylling, 2005). ϵ_a is defined (Heald et al., 2014) as the instantaneous change of radiative flux imbalance across a surface at the top of the atmosphere (or change of net irradiance, in units of W m^{-2}), between the incoming solar radiation and the outgoing broadband radiation from Earth, resulting solely from adding aerosols to a cloudless atmosphere (Fig. 1):

$$\epsilon_a \equiv \Delta F = F_a - F_r \quad (1)$$

where ΔF is the top-of-the-atmosphere (TOA) change of net irradiance, F_a is the TOA net irradiance when aerosols are present, and F_r is the reference TOA net irradiance with no clouds and no aerosols.

Figure 1. Diagram to illustrate the change of net irradiance at the TOA, from a reference condition with no clouds and no aerosols, to a specific aerosol scenario, defining the aerosol radiative effect as: $\epsilon_a = (f_d - f_{u,a}) - (f_d - f_{u,r}) = f_{u,r} - f_{u,a}$. Since land surfaces generally have low reflectivity, $f_{u,r}$ usually has a lower magnitude than $f_{u,a}$, resulting in a negative ϵ_a . See the main text for the definition of each quantity.

In Eq. (1), F_i is defined as the TOA difference between the downwelling solar irradiance f_d and the upwelling broadband (i.e., shortwave and longwave) irradiance $f_{u,i}$, for condition $i = \{a,r\}$ in scenarios with aerosols (a) or reference (r):

$$F_a = f_d - f_{u,a} \quad (2a)$$

$$F_r = f_d - f_{u,r} \quad (2b)$$

Therefore, ϵ_a can be calculated as:

$$\epsilon_a = f_{u,r} - f_{u,a} \quad (3)$$

The literature presents several works that have sought estimates for ϵ_a , employing different techniques, and the authors highlight some caveats. Remer and Kaufman (2006) estimated the global ϵ_a over the oceans to be between $-5.0 \pm 0.6 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ and $-5.5 \pm 0.6 \text{ W m}^{-2}$, based on satellite remote sensing aerosol data. A similar result was obtained by Yu and others (2006), with a global aerosol effect of $-5.5 \pm 0.2 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ over the oceans and $-4.9 \pm 0.7 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ over the continents. These authors indicate that uncertainties in determining the vertical distribution of aerosols on a global scale are one of the problematic factors with this ϵ_a estimate. Another issue raised by the authors is the uncertainty in determining radiative absorption in the particle phase for different aerosol sources (Yu et al., 2006). Kim and Ramanathan (2008) estimated the global ϵ_a (ocean and land surfaces) as $-6.0 \pm 1.0 \text{ W m}^{-2}$, and provided insights into regional variations of this quantity. For instance, zonal ϵ_a means between latitudes -60°N to 0°N show values ranging from approximately -4.0 to -6.0 W m^{-2} (Kim and Ramanathan, 2008). Bellouin and colleagues (2013), based on a reanalysis of aerosol data, estimated ϵ_a to be $-7.7 \pm 1.5 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ over the oceans and $-6.4 \pm 1.0 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ over land. The results of these authors demonstrate a strong seasonality over South America, attributed to the yearly impact of biomass burning aerosols originating from the Amazon Basin. The authors also note that determining the aerosol radiative absorption is a key factor contributing to the uncertainty of ϵ_a estimates (Bellouin et al., 2013).

Heald and colleagues (2014) used a global chemical transport model coupled with a radiative transfer model and estimated the global ϵ_a as -2.75 W m^{-2} . The authors identified that the model used in the study lacked a proper physical and optical characterization of aerosol properties, especially over remote locations, for both marine and terrestrial ecosystems. On the other hand, another study indicated that aerosol absorption in models is biased toward higher values (Brown et al., 2021). Loeb and coworkers (2021) studied ϵ_a temporal trends from 2002 to 2020, at 1.0 degree spatial resolution, and found a worldwide positive trend of $0.077 \pm 0.14 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ decade}^{-1}$ (2-sigma uncertainty), while for central Brazil one can infer from their graphs a positive ϵ_a trend of up to $1.0 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ decade}^{-1}$, associated with a reduction of the aerosol optical depth (AOD) of about 0.10 decade^{-1} (Loeb et al., 2021), from which we imply a decrease of biomass burning smoke emissions. However, this downward trend in AOD might have changed recently. Due to severe drought conditions, the number of fire spots detected by satellite across several biomes in Brazil increased in 2024 relative to recent years. It was the highest since 2010 in the Amazon¹. These accounts underscore the need for a deeper understanding of atmospheric aerosols and their radiative effects across various ecosystems.

We propose calculating ϵ_a for the southern Amazon Basin and the MASP by utilizing remotely sensed data on aerosol properties made available by surface sunphotometers and recent satellite missions, and employing the libRadtran code package to simulate TOA irradiance budgets. The Aerosol Robotic Network (AERONET) is a worldwide network maintained by the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA), composed of solar photometers that perform collimated measurements of direct and diffuse descending solar radiation at the surface, at various wavelengths (Giles et al., 2019; Holben et al., 2006, 1998). There are several AERONET sites in Brazil and South America, including those in the southern Amazon Basin (e.g., Alta Floresta, MT) and São Paulo. Some of them have been active for over twenty years. Measuring the attenuation of direct solar radiation at several wavelengths allows the calculation of the AOD and other quantities. Diffuse radiation measurements allow inferring other average (columnar) physical properties of the atmospheric aerosol, such as its size distribution, complex refractive index, and its extinction phase function.

¹ https://terrabrasilis.dpi.inpe.br/queimadas/situacao-atual/estatisticas/estatisticas_estados/ accessed 2025-05-20.

Two new major satellites were launched in 2024 and will provide the core space sensor data for this project. The EarthCARE mission is a partnership between the European Space Agency (ESA) and the Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency (JAXA) (Wehr et al., 2023), while the Plankton, Aerosol, Cloud, ocean Ecosystem (PACE) mission is managed by NASA (Werdell et al., 2019). The EarthCARE satellite has four instruments: the ATmospheric LIDar (ATLID), the Cloud Profiling Radar (CPR), the Multi-Spectral Imager (MSI), and the Broad-Band Radiometer (BBR). These instruments, operating together, aim to physically characterize complex scenes involving clouds and aerosols in a lateral field of view (swath) of up to 150 km, corresponding to MSI's coverage. The ultraviolet lidar measures vertical profiles of aerosols and thin clouds; the radar has Doppler capability and measures particle velocities in clouds and precipitation rates; the imager has solar and thermal channels to estimate cloud and aerosol properties along the trajectory; the broadband radiometer measures solar and thermal radiance at three angles along the trajectory, for measurements of radiative fluxes at the top of the atmosphere (Wehr et al., 2023). PACE has a hyperspectral imager, the Ocean Color Instrument (OCI), and two multi-angle polarimeters, the Spectro-polarimeter for Planetary Exploration (SPEXone) and the Hyper Angular Research Polarimeter (HARP2). The OCI aims to quantify the concentrations of different phytoplankton species, the distribution of chlorophyll, the concentration of organic carbon or particulate matter dissolved in water, among other products, over the oceans. Across the continents, the OCI measures the hyperspectral reflectance of the surface and derives inferences about aerosols and clouds, including optical depth, thermodynamic phase, and effective radius of solid and liquid particles in clouds, among other parameters (Remer, Davis, et al., 2019). The polarimeters combine hyperspectral (SPEXone) and hyperangular (HARP2) measurements, thereby providing access to a wide range of information about the scattered radiation signal, which enables simultaneous inferences of aerosol and surface properties. It is expected that this configuration design of the polarimeters will allow at least a doubling of the number of degrees of freedom of information obtained from the aerosol layer compared to previous missions. In this way, it will be possible to obtain highly accurate inferences about the physical properties of aerosols, such as size distribution, complex refractive index, or single scattering albedo (Remer, Knobelspiesse, et al., 2019).

In this project, we will characterize aerosols and surface properties at two locations in Brazil using AERONET sunphotometers, PACE/HARP2, and EarthCARE/ATLID data, and then employ this data to run simulations of TOA fluxes with libRadtran to derive ϵ_a . We note that Kato and coworkers (2022) pointed out that part of the uncertainty associated with ϵ_a derivations can be reduced by combining lidar data (such as ATLID) and spectrometer results (e.g., HARP2). Additionally, Chen and colleagues (2022) suggested that remote sensing techniques employing polarimetric sensors, such as HARP2, have the potential to mitigate the uncertainties surrounding aerosol absorption, one of the most significant concerns identified in previous studies, as outlined above.

1.1 Scientific objectives

This plan aims to combine multiple remote sensing data and modeling to derive the aerosol direct radiative effect in two locations in Brazil, one in the southern Amazon Basin (Alta Floresta, MT) and the other in the MASP.

This project has the following specific objectives:

- a) To characterize columnar physical and optical properties of atmospheric aerosols and surface reflectance in São Paulo and Alta Floresta, based on retrievals by AERONET sunphotometers, PACE/HARP2, and EarthCARE/ATLID products, including seasonal variations.
- b) To use the libRadtran code to model the upwelling cloud-free broadband radiative flux at the top of the atmosphere, at each location and season, by employing the

previously derived physical and optical aerosol and surface properties, and estimate the annual aerosol direct radiative effect.

- c) To critically evaluate the resulting estimates by comparing them with independent results in the published literature.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 AERONET retrievals

AERONET photometers perform two types of measurements, involving direct solar radiation and diffuse radiation measurements. Direct radiation is measured by the photometer in cloudless conditions, when its collimator points directly at the sun. Three measurements (triplets) are made, each taking approximately 10 seconds. The triplet sample standard deviation of these measurements is used to detect clouds. The measurement interval between triplets varies throughout the day, typically every 15 minutes or less if no rain is detected. Measurements identified as valid (i.e. cloudless) are used to derive the optical depth of aerosols at wavelengths of 340, 380, 440, 500, 675, 870, 1020 and 1640 nm, the amount of water vapor present in the vertical column, and the Angstrom exponent between wavelength pairs (Holben et al., 1998). For diffuse radiation measurements, the photometer collimator points at the sky away from the direct solar beam, at specific angles, and records the scattered radiation at constant zenith angle (Almucantar scan) or along the solar plane (principal plane scan). Sky radiance measurements are used in AERONET inversion codes to derive quantities such as: scattering phase function, particle size distribution, asymmetry factor, single scattering albedo, and complex refractive index. Diffuse measurements occur less frequently than direct ones because they require more restrictive physical conditions, with the absence of clouds at a certain number of observation angles.

AERONET's internal algorithm processes all measurements as soon as they are made, classifying the data quality into levels 1.0, 1.5, and 2.0 (Holben et al., 2006). Level 1.0 is raw data from successful measurements. Level 1.5 is cloud-screened data, also distributed within a few minutes of acquisition. Level 2.0 data are obtained from periodic intercalibrations of each photometer, using a standard reference photometer maintained by NASA. This intercalibration process requires each photometer to be physically transported to a NASA campus, typically once a year. For this reason, Level 2.0 data can generally be delayed in becoming available, but is preferable for research use. In this project, we will use Level 2.0 data whenever possible and Level 1.5 data otherwise.

2.2 EarthCARE/ATLID and PACE/HARP2 retrievals

EarthCARE has a descending polar orbit with a nominal mean equator crossing time of 14:00 local time, and a repeat cycle of 25 days. EarthCARE's ATLID is a 355 nm lidar that measures vertical profiles of aerosols and thin clouds. ATLID measures atmospheric profiles in a direction shifted 3 degrees off nadir to avoid specular reflections, with a vertical resolution of approximately 100 m from the ground to 20 km altitude and 500 m from 20 km to 40 km altitude. Reflected pulses are collected every 285 m along track and then averaged every 10 km to improve the signal-to-noise ratio in the retrievals. After processing, ATLID measurements generate several products, including some that are especially relevant to this project, such as feature mask and target classification, extinction, backscatter, depolarization profiles, and aerosol properties.

PACE has an ascending polar orbit with a nominal mean equator crossing time of 13:00 local time, and a repeat cycle of 2 days. HARP2 aboard the PACE satellite is a hyperangular imaging polarimeter that provides microphysical information on aerosol particles and clouds, as well as the properties of land and water surfaces. The lateral swath spans 1,550 km, with ground pixels measuring 1.3 x 2.0 km. The sensor measures the polarized radiance at three angles of

linear polarization, in 10 along-track viewing angles for spectral bands of 440, 550, and 870 nm, and 60 viewing angles for a 670 nm band. These measurements are processed to derive microphysical parameters such as the aerosol size distribution, single scattering albedo, complex refractive index, and particle shape, as well as the macrophysical parameter aerosol optical depth.

2.3 Modeling ϵ_a with libRadtran

libRadtran is a freely available software package used to simulate the interaction of shortwave and longwave radiation with the atmosphere and the Earth's surface. It allows the user to configure versatile scenarios by setting up script files that describe several atmospheric and surface properties, such as gaseous composition, vertical temperature and humidity profiles, bidirectional surface reflectance properties, aerosol size distribution, single scattering albedo, complex refractive indices, phase function, and optical depth. The code includes the full solar and thermal spectrum, with wavelengths ranging from 120 nm to 100 μm . libRadtran calculates the radiative transfer in the atmosphere using code that carries out three main steps (Emde et al., 2016; Mayer and Kylling, 2005). First, a preprocessor converts the user-input atmospheric properties, such as aerosol microphysical properties, into optical properties required by the main solver. Next, the radiative transfer equation solver calculates radiances, irradiances, and other quantities needed by the user, given the specified optical properties. The last step is a post-processor that takes the solver output and performs final calculations, such as integrating over a wavelength range and correcting for the Earth-Sun distance, among other tasks.

For this project, we will use libRadtran to simulate the downwelling shortwave and the upwelling broadband radiative fluxes across the top of the atmosphere under cloudless conditions. To achieve this goal, we will begin by characterizing the physical and optical properties of atmospheric aerosols from AERONET, HARP2, and ATLID retrievals at the two selected locations in the project: MASP and Alta Floresta in the southern Amazon Basin. The seasonal characterization of aerosols and the surface reflectance at these locations will provide the core elements to set up the physical conditions for the radiative transfer scenario we will study using libRadtran.

AERONET will provide libRadtran with aerosol microphysical parameters that are key for the flux simulations. AERONET sunphotometers have been running for decades at the two locations. It represents a robust aerosol dataset, but with limited spatial representativeness over the continent compared to what satellite sensors can achieve. On the other hand, HARP2 and ATLID have a relatively short history, having been launched in 2024; however, they can assess atmospheric conditions over much broader areas compared to stationary surface sensors. Therefore, one key step for this project will be comparing AERONET and HARP2 or ATLID retrievals during matchup overpass opportunities. These comparisons will allow us to determine the extent to which the satellite sensors' retrievals can be used to characterize the spatial variability of aerosols' micro- and macrophysical parameters, as well as surface reflectance properties. Specifically, we will study parameters such as the spectral surface reflectance, aerosol optical depth, vertical extinction profile, single scattering albedo, asymmetry factor, size distribution, scattering phase function, and complex refractive index. The spatial patterns obtained for these quantities from HARP2 and ATLID, validated against AERONET data, will enable running libRadtran simulations under realistic representations of the atmosphere and the surface.

In comparing AERONET and HARP2, we note that HARP2's lack of wavelengths above 870 nm indicates its performance might be degraded if seeking to reproduce AERONET's microphysical retrievals for coarse aerosol particles with diameters above 2 μm (Remer et al., 2019). In the context of this project, such a characteristic could potentially be relevant for libRadtran simulations carried out under Saharan dust advection conditions over the central eastern Amazon Basin (Koren et al., 2006; Swap et al., 1992), but this aerosol source has not been reported over the southern Amazon Basin.

Surface properties are also a key parameter to be considered in libRadtran flux simulations, considering that the surface reflectance signal will most likely dominate the upwelling shortwave radiance at the TOA. Depending on the surface reflectance properties, a given aerosol type can have either a positive or negative radiative effect at the TOA (Bellouin et al., 2004; Yu et al., 2006). libRadtran simulations require either a specified surface albedo, spectral albedo, or an assumption of a Bi-directional Reflectance Function (BRDF) class. In this project, the surface reflectance properties will be assessed from AERONET and HARP2 retrievals. Both platforms employ the Generalized Retrieval of Atmosphere and Surface Properties (GRASP²) (Chen et al., 2020). GRASP analyzes measured radiance data and derives aerosol and surface reflectance properties simultaneously, including aerosol size distribution, spectral refractive index, degree of sphericity, and radiative absorption. This algorithm accommodates various sets of boundary conditions, including bright urban surfaces such as the MASP, which has posed a challenge for traditional retrieval algorithms (Rudke et al., 2023).

The height of the aerosol layer, an important parameter for achieving the project goals through libRadtran simulations, can also be derived from HARP2 using the differential attenuation of solar radiation at wavelengths with and without absorption by atmospheric gases. This particular product will be compared with ATLID extinction profiles. The lidar sensor characterizes the vertical profile of aerosols based on direct measurements of laser pulses backscattered by the aerosol particles, determined possibly with a higher degree of precision than the HARP2 algorithm. On the other hand, ATLID's narrow field of view and 25-day repeat cycle result in a much more restricted spatial sampling over the Amazon Basin than what HARP2 can provide. Therefore, we will conduct an intercomparison between the two satellite sensors, which may yield synergistic results in retrieving the height of the aerosol layer for use as input to libRadtran.

3. Expected results and challenges to be addressed

The technical feasibility of the project is discussed next. Access to the relevant datasets to be used in this project is freely available on the internet through several web portals, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Data or code sources and accession addresses.

Source	Accession address
AERONET	https://aeronet.gsfc.nasa.gov/
PACE/HARP2	https://search.earthdata.nasa.gov/
EarthCARE/ATLID	https://ec-pdgs-dissemination2.eo.esa.int/
libRadtran	https://www.libradtran.org/

Although it is expected that the new PACE/HARP2 satellite sensor will produce a wealth of data on aerosol microphysics with an unprecedented level of detail, it is necessary to consider the need to validate such a new source of data. New spaceborne sensors may yield biased estimates for key quantities required in the project, such as the absorption of radiation by aerosol particles, represented, for instance, by the aerosol single scattering albedo. Therefore, one of the steps in this project will be a comparison of aerosol microphysical parameters retrieved by HARP2 and AERONET, the latter being considered the “ground truth” reference. We note that a comprehensive validation of HARP2 products is outside the scope of this project. We will conduct a correlation analysis to investigate how HARP2 variability and biases in key microphysical parameters compare with the well-established AERONET retrievals.

² <https://www.spie.org/news/5558-grasp-a-versatile-algorithm-for-characterizing-the-atmosphere> accessed 2025-05-20.

Deriving ϵ_a requires, among other things, characterizing the surface reflectance. In the absence of clouds, the solar reflectance signal at the top of the atmosphere is mainly determined by surface reflectance. At the same time, the aerosol and atmospheric contributions to the total upwelling radiative flux generally represent a second-order effect under the conditions outlined in this project. In the MASP, the surface reflectance can change or have its area expanded against rural surroundings due to continuous transformations characteristic of the urban environment. In the Amazon, phenological modifications of surface reflectance properties can occur throughout the year, and need to be addressed in the simulations. In recent years, the southern Amazon Basin has also been subjected to increased emissions of greenhouse gases (Da Nobrega and Correia, 2025) due to deforestation activity that affects the overall surface reflectance in irregular patches with varying degrees of logging. To mitigate these issues, we plan to characterize changes in surface reflectance statistically and, if necessary, use spatial and temporal averaging to reduce variability. In the Amazon, in particular, we expect the surface reflectance to show a periodic annual pattern that can be parameterized in the simulations.

Finally, regarding ϵ_a comparisons with estimates derived by other authors, we note that this can be a challenging task. Spatial and temporal variations in the datasets used in each study may yield significant ϵ_a differences, as one of the primary aerosol sources in Brazil, smoke from biomass burning, is subject to large yearly fluctuations due to weather patterns or changes in the enforcement of public policies driven by socio-economic pressures. These variations need to be taken into account for meaningful comparisons. We are aware that, although this is a crucial step, it can also be a time-consuming process.

The expected outcomes of this project will include seasonal estimates of ϵ_a for distinct aerosol sources in the Amazon and the MASP. We aim to contribute to reducing uncertainties in the aerosol direct effect, especially related to aerosol absorption and vertical distribution within the atmospheric column. These results will foster a better understanding of the role aerosols play in Earth's energy budget, which is crucial for improving our overall knowledge of their climatic impact, enhancing climate parameterizations in the future, and informing environmental policy.

4. Timetable

This project is scheduled to last 36 months, as outlined in the following schedule.

Activity	Semester					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Course credits	X	X	X			
Language exam		X				
Characterizing aerosols in the southern Amazon and the MASP		X	X			
Correlation analysis of HARP2 and AERONET		X	X			
Simulation tests and runs			X	X	X	
Statistical analyses, critical comparisons				X	X	X
Publication					X	X
Dissertation writing					X	X
Master's defense						X

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